

Bibliotherapy as a Mental Health Intervention: A Study of ‘Cahaya Yang Hidup Bahagia’ Through Al-Ghazali’s Counselling Theory

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ABSTRACT

This study is an analysis of the novel “Cahaya Yang Hidup Bahagia” by Nur Aisyah. The aim of this study is to identify the issues faced by the main character from the perspective of Imam Al-Ghazali’s Theory. Through the analysis of this novel, the researcher found that a college student faces several problems in his life. It starts with an issue involving his friend, which causes him to become easily angered, and he is diagnosed with bipolar disorder. This novel analysis aims to assess the suitability of using this novel as bibliotherapy material for mental health intervention and how Al-Ghazali’s counseling theory can strengthen the intervention process. The methodology used in this study includes interview analysis, document analysis, and background analysis from the perspectives of place, time, and society. Based on the issues and findings from the data collected, the problems faced by the main character stem from envy, which forces the student to postpone his studies. The process of helping the main character involves several techniques and methods to achieve his goals. The researcher found that the techniques of mujahadah and muraqabah were applied in this work. Imam Al-Ghazali’s theory is suitable and can be used to help the main character return to his original purpose and life goals. This is because the theory addresses the issues of the heart and implements tazkiyatun nafs (purification of the soul) in the main character.

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1. Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) stated in 2022 [18] that good mental health refers to an individual's level of well-being and their ability to manage their own condition and control themselves when faced with problems. This is evident as 1 in 8 people worldwide experience mental health disorders. According to statistics released in 2019, 40 million people were diagnosed with *bipolar disorder* [7]. This issue should not be taken lightly and must be addressed seriously to prevent undesirable consequences caused by this disorder. The severity of this disorder can occur at any time, often when the individual is in a "manic" or "depressed" state. Study shows that *bipolar disorder* is a condition where the sufferer cannot distinguish between feelings of mania and depression [3]. A "manic" state occurs when an individual becomes aggressive and takes risks in any situation, while "depression" happens when someone feels sad, hopeless, fearful, or in pain without any apparent cause, sometimes with suicidal thoughts.

The researcher conducts this study based on Imam Al-Ghazali's theory according to the perspectives of Tajuddin Ninggal and Yatimah Sarmani. This theory is intended to help individuals who have lost direction in life to return to their true life goals, with reliance on Allah [16]. The counseling process promoted in Islam emphasizes several points, including not forcing the client to do something beyond their ability, maintaining dignity, and being sincere solely for the sake of Allah, among others [4]; [12]. The objective of Imam Al-Ghazali's theory is the purification of the soul to cleanse and purify an individual from traits that hinder the development of good character (*mahmudah*) [15]. Some scholar said, this process is an effort to purify the soul, heart, and self from negative traits through *mujahadah al-nafs* and to beautify it with noble qualities [10]; [13].

Al-Ghazali's Counseling Theory is based on the elements of *qalb* (heart), *ruh* (soul), *nafs* (self), and *aql* (intellect), which form the core of this theory. These elements influence both the internal and external traits of an individual. They are important aspects in helping clients overcome the issues they face. Among the techniques highlighted are *musyaratah* (mutual agreement), *muraqabah* (self-monitoring), *muhasabah* (self-reflection), *mu'aqabah* (self-punishment), *mujahadah* (spiritual struggle), and *mu'atabah* (self-criticism). These six techniques are used to assist clients in overcoming issues that affect their well-being.

1.1 Statement Of The Problem

The character in this novel is a student at Darul Huffaz [11]. The story begins when the main character faces issues with his friend and is frequently dissatisfied with his friend's behaviour. This conflict escalates, causing the character to gradually change in terms of his personality. As a result, various other issues arise within him. Consequently, he is sent home to receive treatment from a psychiatric specialist at a hospital. He is diagnosed with *bipolar disorder* and is required to undergo treatment at a Psychiatric and Mental Health Clinic. In addition to the support from his psychiatrist, he also receives emotional support from the people around him.

1.2 Objectives And Research Questions

1.2.1 Objectives of the Study

1. To analyse Imam Al-Ghazali's theory to identify the issues faced by the main character in this novel.
2. To identify the development of the main character in the novel using Imam Al-Ghazali's theory.

1.2.2 Research Questions

1. What issues are faced by the main character in the novel when analysed using Imam Al-Ghazali's theory?
2. What developments occur in the main character using Imam Al-Ghazali's theory?

2. Research Methodology

Based on this novel, the researcher conducted the study using qualitative methods, including interview analysis and thematic analysis, to understand the background of the study as a whole.

2.1 Interview Analysis

In this novel, the researcher identifies several interviews between the psychiatrist and the main character. Additionally, the researcher finds interactions between the main character and his parents, friends, and uncle, who provide emotional support to help him recover.

2.2 Themes Analysis

2.2.1 Background of the Main Character

Based on the novel, the researcher identifies several characters presented by the author. The main character in this novel is Nur, a student from a higher education institution, Darul Huffaz. Nur, who has been diagnosed with bipolar disorder, is receiving treatment at a Psychiatric and Mental Health Clinic. She also undergoes treatment from Islamic healers, such as ustaz (male scholars) and ustazah (female scholars).

Nur's condition began to be recognized when she started having issues with her friend and frequently became angry with them. Her friends were puzzled as they observed her behaviour changing more and more each day. Despite this, the support she received from others helped her remain strong in battling her illness, allowing her to eventually complete her delayed studies.

2.2.2 Living Room Scene

In the living room, Nur suddenly screamed and claimed that she saw blood, even though no one else could see a single drop of blood as she described.

"USTAZ!!! CAN'T YOU SEE THE BLOOD, USTAZ?!"

Nur screamed in the living room of Ayah Chik's house that evening, at dusk. All the onlookers were stunned, frozen in place. What was happening to Nur?

Page 5

The situation in the living room of the house reveals that Nur is experiencing a serious mental disturbance.

2.2.3 Darul Huffaz Islamic Center

Nur was waiting for Haziq at the Darul Huffaz Islamic Center one morning to meet with him. While waiting, a woman named Farah arrived at the Islamic Center at 4:30 AM. They chatted for a while, and Nur shared something with Farah.

"Akak (older sister) is so frustrated waiting for Haziq. Why is he like this? Eeeii, I'm so annoyed with his attitude," Nur suddenly expressed to Farah. "I'm angry. I've never felt this angry at anyone before."

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The Islamic Center was the place where Nur was supposed to meet Haziq. However, Haziq didn't show up until dawn.

2.2.4 Psychiatric and Mental Health Clinic

Nur met with the psychiatrist who was treating her, and a two-way interaction took place between the doctor and Nur.

After Nur calmed down, the doctor began questioning her. The doctor said that she had Bipolar 1 Disorder based on the survey she had filled out earlier. Suddenly, Nur asked permission from her mother to take a book from the bag she was carrying. The book was *Aqidatun Najin*, a book of tauhid (Islamic theology).

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The Psychiatric and Mental Health Clinic was the place where the psychiatrist met with the main character to treat her.

2.2.5 Nur's Family Home

At Nur's house, her uncle gave her a lot of advice about various matters and provided moral support.

"Nur, be patient. A believer will surely be tested. I'll pray for your quick recovery."
"Okay, Pakde (uncle). Thank you for the advice. Thank you also for your prayers. Ameen, Ya Mujib."

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Based on the above interaction, Nur received a lot of advice and support from her family members, including her uncle who came from Indonesia.

2.2.6 Time Setting of the Novel Psychiatric and Mental Health Clinic

Suddenly, Nur pulled out a tauhid book while facing the doctor and handed it to him. Out of the blue, Nur asked her mother for permission to take a book from the bag she was carrying. The book was *Aqidatun Najin*, a tauhid (theology) book.

It was quite amusing—someone going to see a doctor and bringing a *Aqidah* book. Haha. Actually, Nur was trying to deliver a form of da'wah (Islamic preaching), as much as she could. Nur opened the book and began explaining it to the psychiatrist. "Doctor, do you believe what I'm saying?" Suddenly, the doctor's expression changed, as if he had encountered a lion. He looked as though he wanted to run away. The doctor responded, "Yes, I know. But that's not my area of expertise." In a

state of fear, the doctor tried to calm Nur. The respect a younger person should show to an elder must be considered. Thus, Nur made an effort to be respectful. "Sorry, Doctor. I just wanted to share. I feel guilty if I hide knowledge."

Pages 208-209

From this scene, Nur's eagerness to convey something is evident, although the timing was not appropriate. The researcher believes the main character behaved this way due to her strong religious beliefs, leading her to want the psychiatrist to help her from a religious perspective. One of the responsibilities of an advisor is to always use wisdom to meet the client's needs [8]. In this case, the counsellor must use his or her wisdom to manage the situation.

2.3 Society in the Novel

2.3.1 A Caring Society

Nur's father is a caring individual who is attentive to his daughter's health. He took Nur to meet the psychiatrist. "At one point, her father took her to see the psychiatrist. The sign at the hospital read 'Psychiatric and Mental Health Clinic.' Nur felt very sad. 'I'm not crazy, Allah. I'm still sane. Why am I being sent here?' It turned out, she had been there before."

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Nur's father sent her to this clinic to ensure that she would meet with the best doctor and receive proper treatment.

2.3.2 A Loving Society

Nur's mother's loving nature is clear through the messages and advice she gives Nur whenever she leaves the house.

Nur asked her mother for permission to go to the store to buy some things. While giving her permission, her mother reminded her to always recite the Mathurat (a set of supplications).

"Mom, can I go to Mydin with Pakde?"

"Yes, Nur. Be careful. Take care of yourself. Don't forget to recite the al-Mathurat as usual."

"Okay, Mom. Thank you."

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Seeing her daughter in an unstable condition, her mother often reminded her to get closer to Allah SWT.

2.2.3 A Knowledge-Loving Society

Nur always sought opportunities to gain knowledge with her teachers using the books she loved.

"Sis, what's so great about that book? Share it with me." Faizah asked.

"Hmm, I don't know. But this book seems to cover everything. There's so much new knowledge I'm gaining from it. I can't wait to study this book with any ustaz (Islamic scholar) here."

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Nur loves new things that can enhance her life and enjoys sharing them with others.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Analysis based on Imam Ghazali's Theory

The researcher has identified several issues with the main character by analyzing her behaviour using Imam Al-Ghazali's theory. It was found that the main character in the novel, Nur, received treatment from a psychiatrist at the Psychiatric and Mental Health Clinic. She also received moral support from her father, mother, and uncle. The main character, Nur, is shown to have a conflict with her friend, Ahmad Haziq.

"I HATE AHMAD HAZIQ BIN MOKHTAR!!,"

Nur's voice echoed on one floor of the Darul Huffaz girls' dormitory.

"I HATE! HATE! HATE! ARGH!!"

"I swear, I don't want a husband like Ahmad Haziq bin Mokhtar! I will never marry someone like him! Oh Allah... I don't want to!"

Page 29

Nur appears to be angry and confused. She, who has never been angry with anyone, never raised her voice, and never hated anyone, has completely changed from her usual calm self.

Imam Al-Ghazali divides the human soul into three categories: Ammarah, Lawwamah, and Mutmainah. The researcher classifies the main character, Nur, as being in a Lawwamah state, which involves internal conflict between following her feelings or controlling her desires. When the individual is calm, feelings of guilt arise, and they do not want to continue negative behaviour. At this point, the individual is more manageable, more open to discussion, and aware of their mistakes, which can be corrected.

In the novel, the researcher also finds an interaction between the psychiatrist and Nur. Nur meets the psychiatrist to confirm her condition and receive assistance. For example, in their conversation:

"Okay Nur, how are you now? Are you feeling well?"

The doctor asked. "Alhamdulillah, I'm fine, doctor."

"Alhamdulillah. How about the medication? Have you been taking it as prescribed?"

"Yes, doctor." "Bipolar I disorder is a condition that can occur at any time. That's why you have to take the medication for life." "Oh, hmm, I understand, doctor." Although she agreed, Nur found it difficult to accept.

"You will have manic, normal, and depressed phases. Manic is when you feel full of ideas, energy, and willing to spend money on anything. Simply put, you are in a high mood. Normal, like you now, feels just fine, right? No overwhelming ideas. Finally, depressed, which is the opposite of manic. You will feel down and low in mood, what we can also call depression." Nur nodded in understanding.

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Referring to the interaction above, the psychiatrist begins the session by asking about Nur's well-being, which aligns with the first step in counseling as outlined by Imam Al-Ghazali. A counsellor should delve into the client's feelings and understand their struggles. Imam Al-Ghazali also emphasized that counseling should follow proper etiquette, as demonstrated by Prophet Muhammad (SAW). This includes not forcing the client, considering their needs and priorities, and being sensitive to their mental and emotional state. This is in line with Allah's command in Surah An-Nahl (16:125), which says:

"Invite to the way of your Lord with wisdom and good instruction, and argue with them in a way that is best..."

This highlights that a counsellor must use kind, thoughtful words, as stated by past studied [5], using a gentle tone to show sincerity in helping the client.

The "Bipolar Disorder" mentioned by the psychiatrist is an unconscious mental disorder. According to study this disorder refers to extreme mood changes between extreme happiness and severe depression [13]. The mood swings can cause issues such as difficulty sleeping, overwhelming feelings of guilt, and even suicidal thoughts.

In the novel, the researcher finds that Nur receives emotional support to aid in her recovery. Study shows that people with bipolar disorder require emotional support from their families, not just material support [7]. The level of emotional support needed varies based on the severity of the condition. Some patients with Bipolar I Disorder need emotional support during predictable times, while others in more severe stages may need support unexpectedly.

One example of emotional support is the interaction between Nur and her uncle:

"Nur, be patient. A believer will always be tested. Pakde will pray for your quick recovery."

"Okay, Pakde. Thank you for the advice and prayers. Ameen, Ya Mujib."

"You're welcome, Nur. I can only help as much as I can."

"Nur, today I want to share some knowledge with you. First, about the Istikharah prayer.

There's a 'special' supplication. Would you like to know?"

"Yes, of course, Pakde." Nur started taking out a pen and notebook to jot down the new knowledge her uncle was about to share.

"The Istikharah prayer has 4 units of prayer. In each unit, recite Surah Al-Fatihah and Ayat al-Kursi. After two salutations, say this supplication:

اللَّهُمَّ إِنِّي أَسْأَلُكَ بِأَسْمَائِكَ الْأَعْظَمِ الَّذِي أَعْلَمْتَ فِي الْمَكْنُونِ اللَّهُمَّ إِنْ كَانَ هَذَا الْأَمْرَ خَيْرًا لِي فَأَرِنِي بِالْيَاسِي أَوْ الْخَضِرَاءِ وَإِنْ كَانَ شَرًّا لِي فَأَرِنِي بِالْأَحْمَرِ أَوْ الْأَسْوَدِ إِنَّكَ عَلَى كُلِّ شَيْءٍ قَدِيرٌ

This is taken from the al-Ma'arif book, one of the Sufi texts."

Pages 244-246

This interaction shows that her family provides excellent emotional support to Nur. The researcher also analyzes that her uncle's technique can be identified as muraqabah—feeling the presence of Allah. This technique is a process of self-improvement, aiming to carry out religious duties with the consciousness that Allah is always observing our actions and intentions. This helps the individual perform consistent acts of worship and stay aligned with Islamic principles. According to study Imam Al-Ghazali links muraqabah with al-haya (modesty), which is related to al-ihsan (spiritual excellence) [19]. This concept encourages individuals to act as though they can see Allah, or know that He is seeing them, thus guiding their actions in accordance with the teachings of Islam.

Another interaction shows mujahadah—the effort to improve oneself and engage in continuous worship.

"Do you want a prayer to strengthen your heart?"

"Why would I need that prayer, Pakde?"

"When you feel uncertain or lack confidence, recite this prayer. For example, when you're unsure about your wudhu or lack confidence in your prayers. Every time you're about to do something, recite this prayer, and inshaAllah, your heart will become stronger."

"How do I recite it, Pakde?"

سُبْحَانَ الْمَالِكِ الْقُدُّوسِ، سُبْحَانَ الْخَالِقِ الْفَعَّالِ، إِنْ يَشَاءُ يُذْهِبْكُمْ وَيَأْتِ بِخَلْقٍ جَدِيدٍ

"Recite it seven times, placing your right hand on your left chest."

"Oh, okay, Pakde. Alhamdulillah, I've learned something new."

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Based on this interaction, the researcher also finds the presence of mujahadah, which involves striving to overcome low desires and continuously seek self-improvement. Imam Al-Ghazali stated

that the greatest jihad is the battle against the soul's desires, the temptations of the world, and the whisperings of Satan. Islam is both faith and action. Deeds are meaningless without faith, just as faith is incomplete without actions [9]. Those who strive in this way will find Allah's pleasure and be guided toward Paradise. This statement underscores the integral relationship between belief and practice in Islam. Aqidah forms the foundation of a Muslim's conviction in the oneness of Allah, prophethood, and the principles of the faith. Meanwhile, amal refers to the practical application of this belief through acts of worship, ethical behavior, and fulfilling obligations toward Allah and fellow humans.

The Quran [1] highlights this balance in several verses, such as:

"Whoever does righteous deeds while being a believer—he will have no fear of injustice nor deprivation."

(Surah Taha 20:112)

This synergy between iman and amal ensures that a Muslim's spiritual journey is holistic, combining inner conviction with outward obedience to Allah's commands. In conclusion, based on this novel, the main character is determined to gain knowledge and improve herself, helping her overcome challenges. Research suggests that true mujahadah requires strong commitment and desire to leave worldly desires [2], which will ultimately ease one's journey toward spiritual success.

4. Conclusion

The results of this study successfully identified the issues faced by the main character through an analysis based on Imam Al-Ghazali's perspective. The researcher also explored and identified the development of the main character throughout the novel. In conclusion, the work produced can serve as a valuable guide to help those dealing with mental disorders and emotional stress.

5. Implications and Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, Imam Al-Ghazali's theory can help and provide a significant impact on the main character by guiding them to draw closer to the Almighty. The researcher has discovered that this theory is applicable to clients experiencing mental health issues, particularly 'bipolar disorder' as portrayed by the main character. According to study, therapy is an essential component in managing bipolar disorder by eliminating negative thoughts, boosting self-confidence, and much more [14]. Therefore, this theory can serve as a therapeutic approach to help clients adopt a more positive outlook and be more inclined toward doing good.

As a recommendation, the researcher suggests that the author diversify the approaches used with the main character. Additionally, the author could incorporate various interventions so that the book may serve as a reference and guide for those dealing with mental health issues. The researcher also proposes the use of a "list of actions" intervention. Clients can list good deeds they can perform and harmful actions to avoid. The deeds performed would be marked, while unperformed actions would be left unmarked. According to study, the use of a 'mutaba'ah yaumiyah' book helps students stay on track with their daily practices, organizing their routines and increasing discipline [6]. Clients can use this method and have it reviewed by a counsellor to ensure progress. Research indicates that this practice can enhance student discipline and aid personal development, leading to a more organized life.

The second intervention involves holding halaqah (study circles) and usrah (Islamic study groups) to build stronger relationships and foster higher levels of trust between the counsellor and the client. According to study usrah helps Muslims engage in good deeds and integrate Islamic teachings into their lives [17]. It strengthens the bond of Islamic brotherhood, deepens understanding of Islam, and encourages both obligatory and voluntary acts of worship. Studies highlight that several principles should be incorporated into usrah programs, such as the study of Quranic verses, hadiths, the biography of Prophet Muhammad (SAW), and Islamic thought modules [20]. In conclusion, these interventions can be applied across different levels of society while simultaneously improving individuals' lives in the eyes of Allah.

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